

ISSN 0975-4067

KIRANĀVALĪ

Journal of Sanskrit Research Foundation

The New Trivandrum Sanskrit Series

Vol.XV. Book. I-IV

January-December

2023

Sanskrit Research Foundation

T.C 39/37

Thiruvananthapuram-36

KIRANĀVALĪ

Journal of Sanskrit Research Foundation

Editor

Prof. Dr.M. Manimohan (Rtd)

Sree Sankaracharya University of Sanskrit, Kalady

dr.m.manimohan@gmail.com

Executive Editor

Prof. Dr.C.S.Sasikumar (Rtd.)

Sree Sankaracharya University of Sanskrit, Kalady

drsasikumar@gmail.com

Managing Editor

Prof. Dr.G.Narayanan

Sree Sankaracharya University of Sanskrit, Kalady

dr.g.narayanan@gmail.com

Editorial board

Dr.V.Sisupalapanikkar, Professor of Sanskrit(Rtd.) Uty. of Kerala

Dr.K.Muthulakshmi, Professor of Vedanta, S.S.U.S. Kalady

Dr.R.Vijayakumar, Professor of Vyakarana(Rtd.), S.S.U.S.Kalady

Dr.P.Chithambaran, Professor of Vedanta (Rtd),S.S.U.S. Kalady

Dr.P.K.Dharmarajan, Professor of Sahitya, (Rtd) S.S.U.S. Kalady

Dr.K.K.Sundaresan, Associate Professor in Vedanta, SSUS.Kalady

Dr.S.Sobhana, Professor of Vedanta (Rtd), S.S.U.S.Kalady

Dr.T.Devarajan, Professor of Sanskrit (Rtd), University of Kerala

Associate Editor

Dr.R.Jinu

Associate Professor, Dept of English,

Noorul Islam Centre For Higher Education, Kumaracoil,

Thuckalay, Kanyakumari, Tamil Nadu

jichelnu@gmail.com

Contents

Editors Note	5
A Study on the Separate Legal Identities of the Jains Dr. Anindya Bandyopadhyay	7
Śaivism in the Undivided Balasore District of Odisha Dr. Anil Kumar Acharya	19
Gender Taxonomy in Select Sanskrit Texts Dr. Priya Jose K	28
“The Tragic Fate of Katerina”- A Study Based on Alexander Ostrovsky’s ‘The Thunder Storm’ Dr. Jimly.P	39
Vedic Agriculture and its Implementation in Modern Farming: A Review Garima & Namita Joshi	46
Thematic and Psychological Aspects of the Curses in the light of the Mahābhārata- An Analysis. Pratiksha Goswami	57
Ṣoḍaśāṅgahṛdayam - Essentials of Ayurveda in a nutshell N Pooja, A Arhanth Kumar, K. Vidyalakshmi	73
Humanism in the <i>Bhagavadgītā</i> Dr. K.K. Abdul Majeed	80
Script, Language and Writing Technics of Manuscript Tradition in Kerala Dr. Manju P.M	90
Beyond Silence: Empowering Deaf and Hard of Hearing Students in English Language Learning through Multimodal Approaches Sherin Rahman, Dr R Jinu	96
Veda and the social life of women: A thorough study Dr. Moumita Bhattacharya	107
Ontological Conception of Anekantavada: The Realativistic Interpretation of Jainism Dr. Savithri.A	113
A Representation of Women Subjugation in K.R.Meera’s <i>Hang Woman</i> Meera A S, Dr R Jinu	120
Revisiting Law and Order in the rule of king Mattakala as depicted in Dasakumaracaritam Muthuselvi. A	132
Conservation and Management of Forests in The Hindu Vedas Neetu Joshi, Dr. Namita Joshi	137
Lord Rama as a communicator: Excerpts from Shriramcharitmanas Mayank Bharadwaj	144
Hospitality in the light of Indian culture and Sanskrit Sahitya Dr. Hemant Sharma	161
Exploring the Relationship between Translation and Social Behavior: An Investigation of Bible Translation in Malayalam Dr. Pratheesh Peter	172

Pūrva Mīmāṃsā Vs Śaṅkara's Advaita – A Reading of Śaṅkara's Gītā Upasaṃhāra Bhāṣya	Vishnupriya Srinivasan	177
Does Jaina Epistemology Indicate a Many-Valued Logic	Dr. Sabeena P S	185
जगन्मिथ्यात्वस्य चित्सुखप्रतिपादितं लक्षणम्	डा. सन्तोष .सि.आर्	193
महाभारते सूचिताः जीविकाः – एकमध्ययनम्	डा. के. रतीशः	199
अध्यासस्वरूपविचारः शारीरकमीमांसायां सिद्धान्तबिन्दौ च आशङ्कितविरोधपरिहारश्च	डा. अजिकुमार् पि. वि	203
व्युत्पत्तिवादोक्तदिशा कर्माख्यातार्थविचारः	डा. अजिमोन् सी. एस्	209
शब्दार्थचिह्नविनिर्माणे श्रीहर्षस्य कृतित्वम्	ड. साधन-कुमार-पालः	213
चट्टम्बिस्वामिनः दर्शने वेदान्तयोगदर्शनयोः समन्वयः	डा. आनन्द . एस् , डा. मिधुन्. पि	219
वैशेषिकदर्शने सन्निकर्षविचारः	डा. एस्. शिवकुमारः	225
धर्मशास्त्रदिशा शिक्षायां संस्कृतेः मुख्याङ्गत्वविमर्शः	डा. श्रीजित् टि. जि	230
श्री-अरविन्दस्य अद्वैतवेदान्ततत्त्वानुशीलनम्	डॉ. लक्ष्मीकान्तषडङ्गी	234
सद्योवर्षणम्	डा. ईश्वरः	238
विविधशास्त्रेषु प्रतिपादितस्य गुणतत्त्वस्य पर्यालोचनम्	रिया दत्ता	244
काव्यकारणविमर्शः	डा. कृष्णगोपाल पालः	251
मनुसंहितायां प्रतिफलितं सांख्यतत्त्वम्	लाल्टु रुइदास	257
पुरुषार्थानामुत्सन्निरूपणम्	डा. वाणेश्वरजाना	262
आत्मस्वरूपम् – कठोपनिषदि श्रीमद्भगवद्गीतायां च	डा. बिन्दुश्री. के. एस्	269
स्वामिविवेकानन्दस्य जीवनमधिकृत्य प्रणीताधुनिकसंस्कारकृतकाव्यलयेषु सामाजिकमूल्यबोधः	डॉ. सुनीतावर्मन	272
मुख्योपनिषत्सु कर्मविचारः	मौलि एम्	278
रामरायकवेः अद्वैतान्यमतखण्डने जीवेश्वरस्वरूपविमर्शः	विजिता विजयन्. ए	281
वैदिकपरम्परासंरक्षणे श्रीमदनान्दतीर्थभगवत्पादाचार्याणां परमोच्चस्थानत्वम्	डॉ गुरुमध्वाचार्य तिरुमलाचार्य नवली	284
Concept of Ātman in Ayurveda and Tarkaśāstra	Dr. Devan E. M	287
Submission & Subscription		292

Humanism in the Bhagavadgītā

Dr. K.K. Abdul Majeed¹

Humanism

Humanism originated in Italy during the fourteenth century as a part of Renaissance spread all over the Europe in the nineteenth century. The foremost trends in this field are that scholars collected and studied ancient texts and manuscripts from the adjacent countries. Through this continuous judgment, they held that the man is self-sufficient in all activities without the help of God, priest and church. The concept of humanism flourished in nineteenth century. A teacher of classical language and literature in renaissance Italy is defined, by name as umanista, which means humanist, (contrasted with legista teacher of law). In the fifth century there was a similar concept studiahumanitatis, which stood for grammar, rhetoric, history, literature and moral philosophy (Audi 341). The inspiration for these studies came from the discoveries of ancient Greek and Latin text. During this period Plato's complete works were translated and Aristotle's philosophy was studied in detail.

The humanism is defined as any system or mode of thought or action in which the human interest, values and dignity predominate (Stein). It means that the humanism makes up the entire frame work of human thought, in which there is no God, no super human Reality to which man can be related or can relate himself (Saiyidain). It concerns only with the interest, needs, and welfare of human beings and rejects the religious beliefs and principles which regard human beings as not possessing the power or potentiality of solving their own problems (Lamont).

The humanism originated not as a reaction against medieval

1. Associate Professor, Department of Sanskrit, University of Calicut

learning, but as a growth and development within it. Humanism involved a revival of classical studies, based on a more critical approach to existing text, which reinforced by re-discovery of more accurate manuscript and even of higher to unknown texts. These findings expanded the dimension of learning by the introduction of new ideas, and the revival of study of the Greek. This introduction of new methods and new thought inevitably produced a more flexible and less dogmatic approach to knowledge and it paved the way for new method of teaching, and new approach to education (McLean 28).

Many scholars regard that the development of nationalism, the heretical currents of thought, mysticism antagonism to the scholastic alliance of theology and philosophy were the root cause of the beginning of the renaissance and the reformation of European regions. The period triggered a beginning to find fault with the old traditions, with the old language and literature, the art, the theological systems, the political relations of the church and state (Thilly 261). Some scholars believed that the immediate cause of the European humanistic movement was purely intellectual revival among scholars which rapidly developed political and religious overtones. This gradually weakened the medieval church and society (McLean).

Some thinkers observe that the humanism is not an established school of thought, but it has a definite philosophical attitude. It emphasized the worth and dignity of man by rejecting other-worldliness and transcendentalism. It claims that the man is self-sufficient and is able to comprehend the world phenomena, and developed a certain social order without the help of God. It is an outlook towards the approach to man's worldly life and values, which is characterized by the interest in man, concern for man and faith in man's reason and conscious for discriminating perception of truth and goodness (Mehta). Humanists chose to see Man as actor, capable of controlling his own destiny and charging the world around him. They believe that every human being has a basic need to develop his potential to the fullest to progress beyond what he is now. Humanist accepts the Man as a dynamic and interactive in nature, and considers him as a powerful being, capable of adapting himself to his environment and choosing his own course of action in

order to achieve the goals which he has selected for himself (Sivarajan 11). The humanism considered Man as the designer of all things in physical world; hence it grew as a vibrant system of philosophy in modern age. The truth-seekers from Europe like Voltaire, Rousseau, Bentham, Hume, Kant, Franklin, and Jefferson who were interested in the field of man-centered discourse raised the absolute freedom in the society. The Greek philosopher Protagoras states that Man is the measure of all things. In the integral humanism of Mahatma, Geetha. S. Mehta described that the humanism as a philosophical and literary movement which originated in Italy in the second half of the fourteenth century and got diffused all over the Europe. During the epoch of Renaissance, India also witnessed the humanitarian movement with the pioneer ship of leaders like Raja Ram Mohan Roy and Dayananda Sarasvathi. The European humanism had at its Centre, the anti-theistic attitude, but in India it grew with the theistic style. For this Veda-s, Upaniṣad-s, and *Bhagavadgita* were re-visited.

The humanist values which originated and developed in Europe, strongly influenced the National movement in India during the nineteenth and twentieth centuries. Indians, who got western education started re-reading and re-visiting the ancient scriptures in the light of humanistic concept which they imbibed as a part of western education.

Humanism in Bhagavadgita

Bhagavadgita (BG) does not give any direct proof to the existence of thought on humanism, but the entire text overtly and covertly preach the evolution of human beings into better human beings or divine beings. For this BG suggests many means such as action, devotion, yoga, renunciation and so on. BG has been considering two worlds as real, the empirical and transcendental. The former which enclosed the different activities of human beings leads to Ultimate Reality. The latter was the final goal to be achieved.

The human beings are classified in sixteenth chapter of BG which divided into two groups on the basis of personality and interaction - the divine (deva) and the devilish (*asura*), (द्वौ भूतसर्गो लोकेऽस्मिन् दैव आसुर एव च । BG 16/6). The first set builds a positive thought which connotes a higher status in society. The members of the second group always make problems in society. They deny the existence of

any God or unseen power to control all the activities in this universe.

The Divine Person

BG draws a perfect picture of a good man, who possess the following characteristic features of intellectual cleverness, charity, self-control, fearlessness, non-violence, steadfastness, purity of thought, freedom from hatred, humility, austerity, absence of greed, study of scriptures, honour and sacrifices. When a person possesses these qualities, nobody can hate him. He will be very friendly to all, free from egoism and equipoised in pain and pleasure. He will become a man free from all and personal attachments to anybody and become a man with pure and impartial mind (Ghai 74).

The Devilish Person

The man born with a devilish character sees every action with a selfish end. He regards the whole world as his enemy. Devilish people are full of pride and self-conceit and their sacrifices are hypocritical (Sastri 42). They do not know what to do and what not to do. They are not perfect and pure in body and mind. They never believe in truth and do not know how to believe. They explain that the world is unreal, without any grounds and without any God. They feel that the world is brought about by the force of desire and lust. Such persons, having no intelligence, participate themselves in activities which lead to destruction of the world. They are proud, overconfident and have false prestige and greedy lust. Those persons engage themselves in action with evil objective (Ghai 96)².

Fight against evils

On the basis of duty, individuals are categorized into four classes - Brāhmaṇa, Kṣatriya, Vaiśya and Śūdra, introduced by Śrīkrṣṇa, known as system of caturvarṇya. After the longing of the 'varṇa' based caste system, Brahmins got higher status in society and the qualities like austerity, tolerance, purity, honesty, knowledge, wisdom and peacefulness were expected from them as their second nature.

2. दम्भो दर्पोऽभिमानश्च क्रोधः पारुष्यमेव च ।
असौ मया हतः शत्रुर्हनिष्ये चापरानपि ।
इदमद्य मया लब्धमिमं प्राप्ये मनोरथम् ।
आढ्योऽभिजनवानस्मि कोऽन्योऽस्ति सदृशो मया ।
प्रवृत्तिं व निवृत्तिं व जना न विदुरासुराः ।
काममाश्रित्यदुष्पूरंदम्भमानमदान्विताः ।
एतां हृष्टिमवष्टभ्य नष्टात्मानोऽल्पबुद्धयः ।

अज्ञानं चाभिजातस्य पार्थ सम्पदमासुरीम् ॥ BG - 16/4
ईश्वरोऽहमहं भोगी सिद्धोऽहं बलवान्सुखी ॥ BG-16/14
इदमस्तीदमपि मे भविष्यति पुनर्धनम् ॥ BG - 16/13
यक्ष्ये दास्यामि मोदिष्य इत्यज्ञानविमोहिताः ॥ BG-16/15
न शौचं नापि चाचारो न सत्यं तेषु विद्यते ॥ BG - 16/7
मोहाद्गृहीत्वासङ्ग्राहान्प्रवर्तन्तेऽशुचिचृत्ताः ॥ BG-16/10
प्रभवन्त्युग्रकर्माणः क्षयाय जगतोऽहिताः ॥ BG - 16/9

Kṣatriya, the fighter class was engaged in the battle for the protection and sustainment of dharma and the country. Their characteristic qualities are leadership, kindness, egoism, ability to determination, heroism, magnificence and courage in battle. Agronomy, cattle rearing and trade were done by Vaiśya and hard jobs including labour works were assigned to Śūdra (Ghai 110).

The BG appears in Bhisma parvan of Mahābhārata. This classic poem of India which was compiled by Vyāsa in eighteen chapters, portrayed eighteen days incident on the battle field of Kurukṣetra. This conflict is known as battle of dharma, which was won against the evil. After the death of Pāndu, his elder brother Dhītaraṣṭra ruled his kingdom with the help of Bhikṣma and others but Kauravas including Duryodhana disparaged and planned to murder Pāndava-s clandestinely. Duryodhana played many foul tricks to extinguish the Pāndava-s. But they overcame all this and ever, Duryodhana fired up their lac-residence but Pāndava-s escaped wonderfully before the fire caught up and lived happily in another region of the forest. After some years, Pāndava-s appealed to Duryodhana that they do not want kingdom, they will be satisfied with five villages. But Duryodhana did not concede to this request and hence Pandava-s were forced to fight the battle. This is the background of the eighteen days war, fought on Kurukṣetra with the clever assistance of Lord Kṛṣṇa (Gotshalk, intro).

The great combat of Kurukṣetra, fought more than 5000 years ago, is held as a classical war and got well-known as the Mahābhārata. In this war 640 million people were killed in only eighteen days. The most important component of this war was that the Supreme personality of God head Kṛṣṇa was personally present as a participant, not as a fighter but rather as an adviser and charioteer to Pāndava-s (Chaturvedi 43). The great fight between Kaurava-s, and Pāndava-s who were minority, honestly holding up the underlying cause of truth of under the direction of the charioteer Kṛṣṇa is the matter of exposition of the great puzzle of the world (Jhabwala intro).

Individual freedom BG gives a restricted freedom to human creatures which related the ways to attain the ultimate reality which cannot compare with the freedom in physical life. Every school of thought in India holds that this ultimate freedom as the goal

of human life. BG also speaks of these two kinds of freedom. It enunciates numerous paths to fulfill the objectives in sophisticated life to the human beings which will create an ideal and happy social life. In *The Gita and its Culture* R.K. Chatterjee perceives that the Gita teaches, Man can attain self-realization, through these paths. These are the path of selfless action and non-attachment, the path of knowledge and wisdom, the path devotion and total dedication, the path of union with God through meditation and contemplation (Chatterjee intro).

S. Radhakrishnan says that the BG stresses on the individual freedom of choice and way in which man exercises it. His struggle, his sense of frustration, and self-implication are not to be dismissed as errors of the moral mind or mere phase of dialectic process (Radhakrishnan 48). When Arjuna requested Kṛṣṇa as to which was superior, knowledge or action and which could, bring in the higher good, Lord clarified that some men were suited to tread the path of knowledge and others to follow the path of action. Both existed side by side. No one could remain without action. Action is better than inaction. Action is essential even for maintenance of the body (Radhakrishnan 31).

The knowledge of Reality (jñāna) adoration and love (bhakti) for Supreme person and the will to the divine purpose (karma) are the three modes or mārga-s to attain the excellence or ultimate goal of a person. These are distinguished on account of the distribution of emphasis on the theoretical, emotional and practical features; Human beings are of different types - reflective, emotional, and active (Radhakrishnan 53). Kṛṣṇa makes it clear that he did not hate any one, he was friendly to all, free from egoism and was even minted in pain and pleasure. The devotee was fearless, free from joy and anger, pure, impartial, competent, and does not hate anybody. The actual devoted person may be free from attachments (Radhakrishnan 74).

In fact the renunciation means the absence of desire which leads human beings to build a detached work (niṣkāmakarma). A renounced never thinks about the result of the work. A.L. Basham approves with it and supplements that human activities should be treated as a kind of sacrifice. Ritual sacrifices offered in a selfish spirit are sacrifices in name only. All rituals must be implemented in self-

surrender, without affinity to the result (Basham 89).

The yoga is an exceptional term used by BG, which shows practical movements and action of human beings. It shows how the aspirant avoids bodily movements of tolerance, goes to a place free from outside annihilation, chooses a comfortable seat, normalizes his breathing, focuses his mind on one point and become harmonized and detached from all desire for the fruit of action. When he attains this unity, he arrives at a perfect understanding with his fellow beings through sympathy and love and not because it is a matter of duty. A.L. Basham esteems that the BG is an applied arrangement of mental and spiritual development, whereby a man may reach complete transformation. The practice of yoga, in its early phase seems mainly to be sitting completely still with body, neck, and head resting in a straight line and resting thought and senses to make the mind a single point (Basham 88).

Brotherhood in the *Bhagavadgītā*

Brotherhood means that the team spirit of all living beings in a common platform in the empirical world. According to Aristotle “man is a social being” which shows human beings act a great role in a social hierarchy. *Bhagavadgītā* presents the whole development of philosophic thought enclosed as in a nut shell. Rightly understood, it holds all moral science and philosophy. It is the key stone of the arch of morality as well as its criterion, and it is expressed and embraced by the first object of the society-universal brotherhood (Lonakar). S. Radhakrishnan articulates that the BG involves to untrained pressure on human brotherhood. Therefore BG gives emphasis for *Lokasangraha*. The world solidarity requires changing the whole patterns of life of a being (Radhakrishnan 69). The three verses from BG, are quoted below which highlight the reputation of brotherhood.

आत्मौपम्येन सर्वत्र समं पश्यति योऽर्जुन ।

सुखं वा यदि वा दुःखं स योगी परमो मतः ॥ BG - 6/32

विहाय कामान् यः सर्वान् पुमांश्चरति निस्पृहः ।

निर्ममो निरहङ्कारः स शान्तिमधिगच्छति ॥ BG-2/71

सुहृन्मित्रार्युदासीनमध्यस्थद्वेष्यबन्धुषु ।

साधुष्वपि च पापेषु समबुद्धिर्विशिष्यते ॥ BG - 6/9

These rhymes echo the inner mind of a person, who looks

at pleasure and pain alike. Further, BG proposes that one, who surrenders all desires and moves about free from the sense of ego, can achieve a peaceful life. BG also points out that only *yogin* who maintains the equal opportunity to all beings, especially to friends and well-wishers of him, who won in empirical and transcendental world.

***Bhagavadgītā* as a guide**

BG warns human beings of the horrible conditions of the universe by indicating the three gates to hell desire, anger, and greed and it advises that the careful abstinence from all these nature will help a success life in this world also. The hell gates culminate in the disorder of individuality which leads to utter confusion of the social setup of the human beings. O.P. Ghai describes that these evil things may be destroyed by the goodness in human beings. Kṛṣṇa advised Arjuna, and through him, all the human beings to conquer and thus acquire control over his sense (Ghai 32).

BG stands out as a marvelous guide to man's ethical and moral life in this world and also in his journey in the realm of the spirit. Its solutions and answers to the perennial question seem even more relevant to the present age, in which man, despite his achievements, despair, for happiness and peace (Swami Forword). The five factors are as responsible for the completion of any work in this world. They are body, person who acts ego of the person, the different sense organs, diverse efforts, and divine grace (Chatterjee 19).

अधिष्ठानं तथा कर्ता करणं च पृथग्विधम् ।

विविधाश्च पृथक्चेष्टा दैवं चैवात्र पञ्चमम् ॥ BG-18/14

Conclusion

BG, the most vibrant scripture in India, promotes the human values and reflects the life of human being in social organism but it accepts only one reality, *Brāhman*, the creator, sustainer and destroyer of the world. In BG, Kṛṣṇa himself reveals his *brahmānubhava* with physical evidence to Arjuna (*Vibhūthiyoga*) even in which he accepted the empirical existence. Lord Kṛṣṇa explained to Arjuna, that how self-restrain becomes effective and fruitful only when the mind is directed to highest of all values that highest value which is to be the goal is nothing but, 'I am the Absolute Reality that sat that underlies everything, Brahman' (Narayana Prasad 87).

The salient features of BG can be summarized as follows:

1. Gives a brief sketch of the nature of Supreme Being in the universe.
2. Holds that the two worlds exist.
3. Warns of the horrible nature of hell and three doors of it.
4. Mentions the various ways to dharma and allows freedom to choose.
5. Shows the importance of attending to one's own duty rather than others.
6. Promotes to avoid all kinds of attachments to the physical world which leads to evils and passions.

In a search for human values, N.L. Gupta observes that the main motives of the scriptures are to promote basic and essential qualities as truthfulness, co-operation, love and compassion, peace and non-violence, courage, equality, justice, dignity of labour, and common brotherhood of man (Gupta 17). BG contain its own synthetic, holistic philosophy based on a strong foundation. It provides solution to all type of human problems. After all, the BG has its birth from human predicament, dilemma, agony and dejection. The long dialogues in eighteen chapters of this scripture are mainly meant for providing solution to the problems of empirical life (Paṇḍā Prologue) and it is a text on spiritualism of human conduct and values of knowledge with a correct knowledge and experience of permanence of the soul, passing through different forms and bodies (Panoly 28).

The humanistic approaches in the Western countries opened up a new path on logic to individual freedom, positive attitude towards brotherhood, moral values, virtues, peace, love and righteousness. BG does not explicitly assess the entire thought and development on humanism, but it vividly discusses the spirituality based, controlled-human life in the physical world.

Works cited

- Audi, Robert. Cambridge Dictionary of Philosophy. New York, Cambridge University Press, 1999.
- Basham , A.L. The Origins and Development of Classical Hinduism. Delhi, Motilal Banarsidass Publishers Private Limited, 1990.
- Chatterjee, R K. Gita and Its Culture. India, Sterling Publishers Pvt. Ltd, 1 Jan. 1987.

- Chaturvedi, Laxmi Narayan . The Teachings of Bhagavad Gita. Sterling Publishers, 1991.
- Ghai O. P. The Bhagavad Gita : A Clear Simple Guide to Understanding the True Values of Life and Achieving Supreme Happiness and Peace of Mind. Institute of Personal Development ; Distributed by APT Books 1990.
- Gotshalk, Richard. Bhagavad Gītā. Delhi, Motilal Banarsidass Publ., 1985.
- Jhabwala , S. H. Gita and Its Commentators. Popular Prakashan 1991. 1991. Bombay, Popular Prakashan .
- Lamont, Corliss. The Philosophy of Humanism. New York, F. Ungar Pub. Co, 1982.
- Lonakar, V. C. “The Criterion of Morality or Basis of Brotherhood.” Www.theosociety.org, 1891, www.theosociety.org/pasadena/path/v06n07p201_the-criterion-of-morality-or-the-basis-of-brotherhood.htm. Accessed 25 Dec. 2023. Narayana Prasad, Muni. Life’s Pilgrimage through the Gītā. D.K. Printworld Pvt. Ltd., 2005. Paṇḍā, N.C. Bhagavad-Gītā. New Delhi, D.K. Print World Pvt. Ltd, 2009. Swami , Ekatananda,. The Bhagavadgītā, N.S. Edited by N.S. Subramanyan, New Delhi, Vikas Publishing House Pvt. Ltd, 1994.
- McLean, Antonia. Humanism and the Rise of Science in Tudor England. Heinemann Educational Book, 1972.
- Mehta, Geeta S. “The Integral Humanism of Mahatma.” The Paideia Archive: Twentieth World Congress of Philosophy, vol. 36, no. 1, 1 Jan. 1998, pp. 156–160, www.pdcnet.org/wcp20-paideia/content/wcp20-paideia_1998_0036_0156_0160, <https://doi.org/10.5840/wcp20-paideia199836630>. Accessed 25 September. 2023.
- Panoly, V., Gita in Sankara’s own words; foreword by B.D. Jatti S. Paramasivan, Calicut 1975
- Radhakrishnan, Sarvepalli. The Bhagavadgītā. India, Blackie & Son Ltd, 1985.
- Saiyidain, Khwaja Ghulam. The Humanist Tradition in Indian Educational Thought. Asia Pub. House 1966.
- Sastri, Sakuntala Rao . The Bhagavadgita. Bharatiya Vidhyabhavan, 1993.
- Sivarajan, Dr.K. Psychological Foundation of Education. Calicut, Calicut University Central Co-operative Stores, 2011.
- Stein, Jess M. The Random House Dictionary of the English Language. Random House, 1983.
- Thilly, Frank. A History of Philosophy. Allahabad, Central Publishing House, 1996.